

AN EXPLORATORY QUALITATIVE COMPARISON OF HUMAN EXPERT AND AI-BASED IEC 62443 RISK ASSESSMENTS

PREPRINT, COMPILED DECEMBER 31, 2025

Mathias Pfister ¹

¹Independent Researcher

ABSTRACT

ICSs in critical infrastructure require structured cybersecurity risk assessments, particularly during early design phases in which proposed system architectures must be secured before tendering or procurement. Standards such as IEC 62443 provide established methodologies for this purpose, but assessments are typically performed by human experts and rely on qualitative judgment. Recent advances in LLMs raise the question of whether such systems can support early-stage, standards-based ICS risk assessments. This paper presents an exploratory qualitative comparison of initial risk assessments generated by a LLM and by a human expert team using a common system model and an IEC 62443-3-2-based task set. The results highlight qualitative differences in threat identification, risk prioritization, and architectural coherence, and suggest that LLMs may complement, but not replace, human expertise in early-stage, safety-critical ICS risk assessment.

Keywords Risk Assessment · Industrial Control Systems · ISA/IEC 62443 · Artificial Intelligence · Cybersecurity

1 INTRODUCTION

Industrial Control Systems (ICSs) form the backbone of critical infrastructure and are increasingly exposed to cyber threats due to growing connectivity and the convergence of Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT). In safety-critical environments, structured cybersecurity risk assessments are therefore essential. Standards such as the ISA/IEC 62443 series (hereafter referred to as IEC 62443) provide established methodologies for identifying threats, estimating risk, and deriving security requirements for industrial automation systems.

In industrial practice, such assessments are often conducted at early project stages, for example when a business proposes a system architecture that must be secured before entering a tender or procurement phase. These initial risk assessments are typically performed by human experts relying on domain knowledge and qualitative judgment. While effective, this process is time-consuming and may lead to variability in results. At the same time, recent advances in Large Language Models (LLMs) have demonstrated their ability to generate rapid and structured analyses across technical domains.

Recent surveys indicate that LLMs can support structured reasoning and analytical tasks in cybersecurity, and initial studies suggest that they may improve coverage and consistency in structured threat modeling activities [1, 2].

However, their suitability for supporting professional, standards-based ICS risk assessments in such early design phases has not yet been systematically evaluated.

This paper addresses this gap by comparing initial risk assessments generated by a LLM with those produced by a human expert team. Using a common system model and a standardized task set based on IEC 62443-3-2 [3], the study analyzes differences in identified threat scenarios, risk categorization, and prioritization. The objective of this work is exploratory and aims to provide insights into the potential role and limitations of LLMs as a support tool for early-phase ICS cybersecurity

risk assessments, particularly in the context of system design and tender preparation. The study does not claim statistical generalizability or determine superiority of either assessment approach.

This study compares the resulting risk assessment artifacts produced by human experts and an Artificial Intelligence (AI)-based system under controlled conditions, rather than the assessment processes themselves. The focus is on structural characteristics, internal consistency, and architectural implications of the resulting artifacts, not on cognitive or procedural equivalence between assessors.

2 BACKGROUND

This section outlines the background and related work relevant to AI-based cybersecurity risk assessment in industrial control systems. It summarizes existing research on the application of artificial intelligence in cybersecurity and identifies gaps with respect to IEC 62443-aligned, early-stage risk assessment. This context motivates the comparative approach adopted in this study.

2.1 Industrial Control System Security and IEC 62443

ICSs differ fundamentally from traditional IT systems due to their tight coupling with physical processes, long operational life cycles, and safety-critical functions. Cybersecurity incidents in ICS environments may therefore lead to physical damage, service disruption, or safety hazards, rather than solely information loss [4, 5]. This perspective is also reflected in established industrial security guidance such as NIST Special Publication 800-82, which emphasizes availability, integrity, and safety over confidentiality in ICS environments [6].

The IEC 62443 series provides an internationally recognized framework for securing industrial automation and control systems across organizational and technical dimensions [7, 8, 3, 9]. Central to the standard are the concepts of security zones and

conduits, which structure system architectures according to trust boundaries and controlled communication paths. IEC 62443-3-2 defines a qualitative, risk-based assessment process for early system design, in which threat scenarios and consequences are used to derive security requirements and target security levels [3]. Resulting security requirements are specified through security levels and foundational requirements in IEC 62443-3-3 [9].

2.2 Risk Assessment in Safety-Critical and Industrial Systems

Risk assessment is a central activity in safety-critical system engineering, supporting early identification and mitigation of unacceptable risks. Cybersecurity risk assessment in ICSs relies heavily on expert judgment due to system heterogeneity, long life cycles, and safety constraints [4]. Standards such as ISO 31000 describe risk assessment as an inherently qualitative process involving uncertainty and expert judgment [10]. In industrial contexts, especially during early design phases, risk assessments are performed on abstract system architectures and rely on assumptions regarding operational conditions and threat exposure.

Prior studies indicate that risk assessments conducted by different experts may yield varying but equally defensible outcomes, even when standardized methods are applied [4]. Risk assessments may therefore admit multiple defensible outcomes depending on assumptions, system interpretation, and expert perspective [11].

In ICS environments, assessment outcomes directly influence architectural decisions such as segmentation, access control, and security level selection. Excessive architectural complexity introduced through risk-driven design can also negatively impact system operability and life cycle cost, highlighting the need for balanced, context-aware risk assessment [5].

In safety-critical ICS, cybersecurity incidents may directly propagate into physical safety hazards, reinforcing the need for integrated safety-security analysis [5].

2.3 AI-Based Cybersecurity Risk Assessment

Artificial intelligence has been widely studied in cybersecurity, particularly for intrusion detection, vulnerability analysis, and threat intelligence processing. Recent advances in LLMs have shown potential for supporting analytical tasks such as threat modeling and structured security analysis [1]. Initial studies suggest that LLMs can affect coverage and consistency in security-related reasoning tasks [2].

At the same time, the application of AI-based systems in safety-critical contexts remains constrained by challenges related to interpretability, assurance, and trustworthiness, which have been identified as fundamental AI safety concerns in earlier work [12]. These challenges are particularly relevant in ICSs environments, where security assessments directly inform safety-relevant architectural and design decisions.

However, most existing AI-based cybersecurity research focuses on IT-centric systems or operational security use cases and does not address the specific constraints of industrial control systems. Moreover, there is limited empirical work evaluating AI-generated analyses against human expert assessments within established industrial standards. In particular, the applicability

of LLMs to IEC 62443-3-2-aligned, early-stage ICS risk assessments remains largely unexplored, motivating the comparative study presented in this paper.

3 METHODOLOGY

This section describes the methodology used to conduct the comparative risk assessment study. It outlines the assessment framework, system model, task structure, and evaluation criteria, as well as the procedures applied for the human expert and AI-based assessments. The goal is to ensure transparency and comparability of the two assessment approaches.

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a controlled comparative evaluative design to examine differences between risk assessments conducted by an AI system and by a team of human security specialists. The comparison is grounded in the IEC 62443 standard series and is performed on a single, hypothetical but technically realistic industrial automation system.

The independent variable is the type of assessor (AI-based vs. human expert), while the dependent variables relate to the content, structure, and outcomes of the resulting risk assessments. By holding the assessed system and methodological inputs constant, the study isolates assessor-related effects.

3.2 System under Consideration

The system under assessment is a fictive tunnel ventilation system, selected as a representative example of a safety-critical industrial automation environment. Tunnel ventilation systems combine distributed field devices, real-time control, centralized supervision, and direct coupling between cyber integrity and physical safety outcomes, making them suitable for IEC 62443-based risk assessment.

The system architecture was intentionally derived from a business-driven design perspective, reflecting common industrial practice in which functional and operational objectives are defined prior to systematic cybersecurity consideration. As a result, the baseline system is not optimized for cybersecurity or safety, providing a realistic starting point for evaluating assessor-driven risk identification and interpretation.

Figure 1 illustrates the baseline system architecture provided as common input for both the human expert and AI-based risk assessments.

All assessors were provided with a single authoritative system description (System Description.pdf), defining the System under Consideration and describing each component. The document also specifies two operational use cases:

- (1) Normal Operation - Air Quality Control and
- (2) Fire Scenario - Smoke Extraction.

The inclusion of both normal and emergency operating modes introduces differing consequence severities while maintaining a constant system architecture, thereby enabling comparative analysis of risk prioritization, security level determination, and requirement mapping. This controlled but non-ideal system context supports a focused comparison of AI-based and human ex-

Figure 1: Baseline system architecture used as the common input for both the human expert and AI-based risk assessments.

pert IEC 62443 risk assessments while minimizing confounding effects related to system maturity or documentation asymmetries.

3.3 Assessors

3.3.1 Common Assessment Inputs

To ensure comparability, both the AI-based assessor and the human expert team received identical input material without any additional explanations, annotations, or clarifications. The assessment inputs consisted of three documents:

- **System Description.pdf**
This document describes a fictive tunnel ventilation system, including its purpose, architecture, and components. The system ensures air quality during normal operation and performs safety-critical smoke extraction during fire scenarios. The architecture comprises enterprise, screened, operations and monitoring, and automation networks, with components such as Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs), Human-Machine Interfaces (HMIs)/Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), operator and engineering workstations, historians, remote access infrastructure, sensors, jet fans, and dampers. Two operational use cases are explicitly defined: Normal Operation - Air Quality Control and Fire Scenario - Smoke Extraction, which introduce differing operational priorities and consequence severities while maintaining a constant system architecture.
- **Task Description.pdf**
This document defines the assessment task and expected outputs based on an IEC 62443-3-2-oriented risk assessment process. It specifies six structured activities, including identi-

		Consequence				
		Negligible 1	Minor 2	Moderate 3	Major 4	Catastrophic 5
Likelihood	Almost certain 5	Moderate 5	High 10	Extreme 15	Extreme 20	Extreme 25
	Likely 4	Moderate 4	High 8	High 12	Extreme 16	Extreme 20
	Possible 3	Low 3	Moderate 6	High 9	High 12	Extreme 15
	Unlikely 2	Low 2	Moderate 4	Moderate 6	High 8	High 10
	Rare 1	Low 1	Low 2	Low 3	Moderate 4	Moderate 5

Figure 2: Risk matrix provided as part of the assessment task definition and applied consistently in both the human expert and AI-based assessments.

fication of the ten most relevant threat scenarios, prioritization of consequence categories, estimation of likelihood and consequence, definition of security requirements, zoning and conducting of the system, and derivation of Security Level Targets (SL-Ts). The document also provides a risk matrix (see Figure 2). It defines an organizational risk posture characterized by a moderate risk appetite and a very low risk tolerance, and instructs assessors to document assumptions and reasoning where necessary.

- **Answer Sheet.pdf**

The answer sheet provides a standardized reporting template for the assessment results. It structures the output into predefined tables covering threat scenarios, consequence categorization and scaling, likelihood and consequence estimation, security requirements or countermeasures, zoning and conducting decisions, and SL-Ts estimation per zone and conduit. The template enforces explicit documentation of assumptions, rationale, and comments, thereby supporting traceability, comparability, and third-party review of the assessment outcomes.

No assessor was permitted to introduce external system knowledge or undocumented assumptions beyond the provided material. This approach ensured that all observed differences in assessment outcomes can be attributed to assessor interpretation and reasoning rather than to variations in input information.

3.3.2 AI-Based Assessment

The AI-based assessment was conducted using ChatGPT with the GPT-4.1 model, accessed via the standard web interface. The model was used exclusively as an assessment tool to generate risk assessment outputs based on the provided input materials and task description. No external tools, plugins, retrieval mechanisms, or iterative refinement steps were employed.

The assessment was executed as a single controlled run using default system settings. All responses were generated using the model's default inference settings, without tuning stochastic decoding or output variability. The AI system was provided with uploaded textual, architectural, and visual system documentation.

The assessment was executed using a predefined prompting protocol, which included:

- A common set of input documents shared with the human assessors.
- A model identification step to record the model name reported by the system.
- A task prompt instructing the model to perform the defined risk assessment tasks based on the provided system description and to record the results in a structured answer sheet.

The AI-based assessment was performed in a single controlled session using a newly created standard user account. Its outputs were analyzed comparatively against the human expert assessment to examine methodological characteristics, coverage, and structural differences, rather than to establish objective correctness, in early-stage IEC 62443-based risk assessment. All prompts and outputs were retained to enable reproducibility and auditability.

It is acknowledged that LLM-based systems are, in principle, capable of engaging in more elaborate analytical reasoning, iterative refinement, or deeper architectural exploration when explicitly instructed to do so. In this study, however, the AI system was intentionally instantiated in a constrained, single-pass configuration to mirror a common and pragmatic usage pattern in early project phases. The comparison therefore does not reflect the upper bound of LLM analytical capability, but rather examines how an unconstrained human expert process compares to a minimally orchestrated AI-based analysis under identical informational inputs.

3.3.3 Human Expert Assessments

The human expert assessment was conducted by a team of three security specialists with an average of three years of professional experience in industrial cybersecurity and prior experience applying IEC 62443. The expert team represented a typical industrial cybersecurity assessment team, rather than senior principal architects, reflecting a common practice in early-stage project risk assessments.

As assessment input, the experts received exactly the same three documents described in the Common Assessment Input section, without any additional explanations or guidance. The experts were explicitly instructed not to use artificial intelligence tools or LLMs during the assessment. To reflect established professional practice, they were permitted to consult publicly available sources using conventional internet search methods.

The assessment was performed as a facilitated expert workshop, resulting in a single consolidated risk assessment. Differences in interpretation were discussed and resolved through consensus. Key assumptions and decision rationales were documented to ensure traceability of the final assessment outcome.

Public sources were used only for general reference and not to introduce system-specific knowledge beyond the provided assessment inputs.

3.4 Assessment Output Normalization

To enable systematic comparison, outputs from both assessment conditions were normalized into a common analytical structure, including:

- 10 most relevant threat scenarios
- Prioritize the consequence categories
- Estimate the likelihood and consequence
- Define the 10 most appropriate (price vs value) Security Requirements
- Separate the system into Zones and Conduits
- Estimate for each Zone and Conduit an SL-T
- Final System Architecture

This normalization was performed without modifying the substantive content of the assessments.

3.5 Comparative Evaluation Criteria

To compare the AI-based and human expert risk assessments, task-aligned comparative evaluation criteria were defined, broadly aligned with the six IEC 62443-3-2 assessment tasks. The criteria assess standards-consistent assessment characteristics, operationalized through consistency, completeness, plausibility, and alignment with IEC 62443. Absolute correctness against an external ground truth is not assumed, as qualitative, expert-driven risk assessments admit multiple defensible outcomes.

Assessment outputs were compared using the following criteria:

- Threat scenarios: coverage of system components and operating modes, relevance to the defined use cases, and technical specificity.
- Consequence prioritization: internal consistency, plausibility of consequence scaling, and conformance with IEC 62443-3-2 intent.
- Likelihood and consequence estimation: coherence between scenarios and assigned values, consistency across comparable scenarios, and transparency of assumptions.
- Security requirements: traceability to identified threats, appropriateness with respect to the price-value criterion (i.e., proportionality between security benefit and implementation effort), and alignment with IEC 62443 foundational requirements.
- Zones and conduits: architectural coherence, justification quality, and consistency with IEC 62443 zoning principles.
- SL-Ts: plausibility relative to identified risks, granularity across zones and conduits, and internal consistency.
- The final system architecture produced by each assessment was evaluated as an integrative artifact, focusing on structural coherence, alignment with identified risks, and traceability to earlier assessment steps.

Across all tasks, comparison was conducted as a structured qualitative analysis emphasizing explainability, assumption transparency, and internal consistency. Process-oriented characteristics (assessment duration, effort distribution, resource use, reproducibility) were documented separately to contextualize

practical applicability and were not treated as indicators of assessment quality.

Several evaluation dimensions, such as architectural coherence, operational feasibility, and manageability, are inherently normative and reflect established industrial control system design conventions. These criteria intentionally privilege interpretability, operability, and life cycle feasibility over formal risk differentiation. The comparison therefore evaluates practical usefulness for early-stage industrial decision-making, rather than abstract optimality under unconstrained risk minimization.

Architectural coherence was assessed qualitatively, based on the clarity of trust boundaries, the consistency of data flow directionality, and the explicit placement of security enforcement points at zone and conduit interfaces.

3.5.1 Comparability and Scope

The comparison is intentionally asymmetric with respect to consolidation. The human expert assessment represents a consensus artifact produced through discussion and negotiation, whereas the AI-based assessment represents a single, unreviewed analytical artifact. This asymmetry reflects typical real-world usage, where human assessments are socially consolidated while AI outputs are often consumed as preliminary analytical inputs. The observed differences therefore highlight where human consolidation adds value beyond formal analytical decomposition.

The objective of this study is not to establish equivalence or superiority between human and AI assessors, but to examine how different assessment instantiations manifest in early-stage IEC 62443-based risk assessment artifacts when applied to the same system description and task structure.

3.6 Limitations

The study is subject to several limitations. The use of a hypothetical system may not capture all socio-technical complexities of real-world environments. Several authors have highlighted the inherent limitations and variability of qualitative risk estimation approaches when used without empirical grounding [13].

The AI system's outputs may exhibit non-determinism, and the human expert sample size is limited. The AI assessment reflects one model version and one prompting protocol; results may change with different model versions, system settings, or repeated runs. Furthermore, the study does not claim objective correctness of either assessment, but rather compares methodological characteristics and outcomes.

4 RESULTS

This section summarizes the results obtained from the application of the IEC 62443-3-2-inspired risk assessment methodology to a tunnel ventilation system. The results are presented separately for the human expert and the AI-based assessments to enable a structured comparison of outcomes across all assessment tasks.

4.1 Results of the human expert assessment

The human expert assessment identified threat scenarios primarily related to unauthorized access, malware introduction via

maintenance or engineering systems, and manipulation of control logic affecting ventilation behavior. These threat scenarios were described in relation to observable system behavior and potential impacts on ventilation control, with particular emphasis on emergency and fire operating modes.

In the prioritization of consequence categories, safety-related and operational consequences were ranked highest across the assessed scenarios. Environmental, financial, regulatory, and reputational consequences were assigned lower priority and were typically associated with secondary effects following safety or operational impacts. Notably, the quantitative consequence ratings for this task were largely consistent between the AI-based and human expert assessments.

The defined security requirements focused on access control and operational protection measures, including controlled maintenance access procedures, role-based authorization, technically secured remote access mechanisms, and protection of engineering interfaces. The requirements were linked to the identified threat scenarios and documented within the standardized reporting template.

The zoning and conduit structure separated automation components, engineering systems, and enterprise IT assets into distinct zones. Communication paths between zones were defined to support operational and maintenance workflows. Security level targets were assigned across zones and conduits, with higher SL-T values associated with zones containing safety-critical automation functions.

The final system representation reflected the defined zoning, conduits, and security level targets and exhibited a hierarchical separation of enterprise, engineering, and automation domains consistent with a layered industrial control system architecture.

4.2 Results of the AI-Based Analysis

The AI-based assessment, using the GPT-4.1 model, identified threat scenarios covering a broad range of attack techniques, including wireless-based attacks, false data injection, and compromise of update mechanisms. Several of these techniques correspond to established adversary behaviors documented in the MITRE ATT&CK framework for Industrial Control Systems [14].

The threat scenarios primarily addressed integrity- and availability-related attacks and described manipulations that could influence system state or monitoring information, while confidentiality-related aspects played a secondary role.

In the prioritization of consequence categories, safety-related and operational consequences were ranked highest. Environmental, regulatory, and reputational consequences were treated as distinct categories and consistently ranked below safety-related and operational consequences.

The defined security requirements emphasized technical control measures, including authentication mechanisms, secure update processes, logging and monitoring functions, and integrity protection. The requirements were formulated in a standardized manner and documented within the structured reporting template.

The zoning and conduit structure subdivided the system into multiple zones based on identified trust boundaries and access paths. Communication paths between zones were defined as conduits and documented as security-relevant interfaces. Security level targets were assigned across zones and conduits, with differentiated SL-T values corresponding to exposure assumptions and identified threat surfaces.

The final system representation reflected the defined zoning, conduits, and security level targets and included dedicated zones for update services, remote access, engineering functions, and automation components.

4.3 Comparative Results Summary

Both the human expert and AI-based assessments identified safety-critical automation components, engineering systems, and communication interfaces as primary security-relevant elements. In both cases, threat scenarios were associated with potential loss of control or incorrect behavior of the tunnel ventilation system, including impacts on emergency and fire operation modes.

The assessments differed in the scope and structure of identified threat scenarios. The human expert assessment consolidated multiple threat vectors into a smaller number of high-level, architecturally oriented scenarios related to unauthorized access, malware introduction via engineering or maintenance systems, and manipulation of control logic. In contrast, the AI-based assessment enumerated a broader range of threat scenarios, including wireless-based attacks, false data injection, and compromise of update mechanisms.

Both assessments ranked safety-related and operational consequences highest. The human expert assessment treated environmental, regulatory, financial, and reputational consequences as lower-priority and often implicitly linked to safety or operational impacts, whereas the AI-based assessment distinguished these categories more explicitly within its prioritization structure.

Security requirements in both assessments addressed access control, protection of engineering interfaces, and separation between enterprise and automation domains. The human expert assessment emphasized operational and organizational measures, whereas the AI-based assessment emphasized standardized technical control measures.

Both assessments separated enterprise IT, engineering functions, and automation components into distinct zones and identified inter-zone communication paths as security-relevant conduits. The human expert assessment defined fewer, functionally grouped zones, while the AI-based assessment defined more granular zones based on trust boundaries. Higher security level targets were assigned to automation zones and conduits in both assessments, with the AI-based assessment applying more differentiated SL-T values.

5 DISCUSSION

This section discusses the results of the comparative risk assessment and interprets the observed differences between the human expert and AI-based assessments. The discussion focuses on methodological characteristics, limitations, and implications for early-stage IEC 62443 risk assessment.

Table 1: Comparison of threat scenarios identified by the human expert and AI-based assessments.

Human Expert	AI-based
H1: Manipulation or Withholding of Process Data	A1: Unauthorized remote access
H2: Malware Infection via Phishing or Software Downloads	A2: PLC logic manipulation
H3: Compromise of Central Patch Distribution Server	A3: Malware via engineering laptop
H4: Social Engineering-Based Credential Compromise via Jump Host	A4: HMI/SCADA compromise
H5: Deletion of Security and Audit Logs	A5: Sensor spoofing
H6: Unauthorized Full System Control via SCADA	A6: Denial of Service on automation network
H7: Manipulation of Alarm Thresholds (CO / NOx)	A7: Insider misuse
H8: Injection of False Process Data into SCADA	A8: Patch management compromise
H9: Malware Introduction via Removable Media	A9: Historian data manipulation
H10: Unauthorized External Network Access via Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN)	A10: Wireless access abuse

5.1 Threat Scenario comparison

This subsection compares the threat scenarios identified by the human expert and AI-based assessments with respect to coverage of system components and operating modes, relevance to the defined use cases, and technical specificity.

Both approaches identified largely overlapping security-relevant components, including automation devices, engineering systems, maintenance interfaces, and internal networks. In both assessments, threat scenarios were linked to loss of control or incorrect behavior of the ventilation system, particularly in emergency and fire operating modes, indicating convergence on the system's safety-critical functions. Table 1 summarizes the threat scenarios identified by the human expert and AI-based assessments.

Differences were primarily observed in how threat scenarios were structured. Human experts framed threats in terms of operational sequences and system behavior, whereas the AI-based assessment enumerated more technically differentiated attack vectors, such as false data injection and wireless access, with less explicit embedding into operational workflows.

Overall, both assessments covered the key components and operating modes of the system. The human expert scenarios were more closely tied to operational context, while the AI-based scenarios emphasized technical completeness and differentiation, reflecting differing analytical perspectives in early-stage IEC 62443 risk assessment.

5.2 Consequence prioritization

This subsection compares consequence prioritization in the human expert and AI-based assessments with respect to internal consistency, plausibility of consequence scaling, and conformance with the intent of IEC 62443-3-2.

Table 2: Comparison of consequence category prioritization in the human expert and AI-based assessments.

Human Expert		AI-based	
Prio.	Category	Prio.	Category
Very high	Safety	1	Safety
High	Operational	2	Operational
High	Financial	3	Regulatory
Medium	Regulatory	4	Environmental
Medium	Environmental	5	Reputation
Low	Reputation	6	Financial

Both assessments consistently ranked safety-related consequences as the highest priority, reflecting the safety-critical role of the tunnel ventilation system during emergency and fire operating modes. Operational consequences (availability and integrity) were also ranked highly in both assessments, indicating convergence on the dependency of safety functions on reliable system operation. Across the assessed scenarios, the quantitative prioritization of consequences was largely comparable between the human expert and AI-based assessments.

Table 2 summarizes how consequence categories were prioritized in the human expert and AI-based assessments. Differences were observed in the treatment of secondary consequence categories. The human expert assessment applied a more compact prioritization, emphasizing safety-related and operational consequences, with environmental, regulatory, and reputational impacts generally ranked lower and financial consequences rated highly where relevant. This resulted in a consistent but less differentiated consequence hierarchy.

In contrast, the AI-based assessment explicitly distinguished all consequence categories within a structured hierarchy, while ranking financial consequences lowest despite their relevance in the task definition.

Both approaches remain consistent with the intent of IEC 62443-3-2 [3], which emphasizes safety and operational impact as dominant drivers in industrial risk assessment. The observed differences indicate alternative interpretations of how explicitly secondary consequences should be represented in early-stage assessments, balancing pragmatic simplification against formal completeness.

5.3 Likelihood and Consequence Estimation

This subsection compares likelihood and consequence estimation in the human expert and AI-based assessments with respect to coherence between scenarios and assigned values, consistency across comparable scenarios, and transparency of underlying assumptions.

Both assessments assigned the highest consequence values to scenarios affecting safety-critical ventilation functions, particularly during emergency and fire operating modes. In both cases, elevated risk ratings were primarily driven by high consequence rather than high likelihood, indicating a shared emphasis on potential safety impact.

Figure 3 provides a comparative visualization of likelihood and consequence estimation outcomes across the two assessment

Figure 3: Comparison of likelihood and consequence estimation outcomes between the human expert and AI-based assessments.

approaches. Differences are primarily observed in likelihood estimation and value differentiation.

The human expert assessment tended to assign similar likelihood and consequence values to comparable scenarios, reflecting a more consolidated representation of risk rather than a fine-grained numerical differentiation. This reflected an implicit consideration of existing controls and established operational practices.

Although the AI-based assessment used more finely resolved likelihood and consequence values, the overall distribution of risk levels across scenarios was similar.

Both assessments employed identical quantification schemes, enabling direct comparison. The human-based assessment classified six scenarios as extreme risk and three as high risk, whereas the AI-based assessment showed the inverse pattern, with three extreme- and six high-risk classifications.

Overall, both approaches demonstrated internal coherence between scenarios and assigned values. The human expert assessment emphasized consistency across similar scenarios, while the AI-based assessment emphasized transparency and differentiation of assumptions, highlighting differing approaches to risk characterization in early-stage IEC 62443-3-2-aligned assessments.

5.4 Security Requirements

This subsection compares the security requirements defined in the human expert and AI-based assessments with respect to traceability to identified threats, appropriateness in relation to the price-value criterion, and alignment with IEC 62443 foundational requirements.

Alignment with IEC 62443 was assessed qualitatively by mapping identified security requirements to the foundational requirements defined in IEC 62443-3-3 [9] and by verifying the

Table 3: Security requirements derived by human expert and AI-based assessments.

Human Expert	AI-based
Secure network access (Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA), Hardening, Jump Host)	MFA + time-limited Virtual Private Network (VPN) access
Segment IT and OT networks	Application whitelisting
Harden systems using secure baselines (CIS benchmarks)	PLC write protection + change approval
Monitor networks and logs for attacks	Centralized logging and monitoring of security events
Deploy patches in a controlled manner	Network segmentation + Quality of Service (QoS)
Train staff on security threats	Malware protection on engineering and maintenance systems
Implement Backup and Restore concept (for config and log files)	Signed updates + offline testing
Encrypt network communications	Read-only data flow from OT (historian protection)
Restrict physical access to systems	Detection and response mechanisms for security incidents
Enforce role-based access control	WPA3-Enterprise + VLAN isolation

plausibility of assigned SL-Ts relative to the identified threat scenarios. The assessment focused on conceptual consistency and standards alignment rather than exhaustive requirement-by-requirement verification.

Table 3 summarizes the security requirements defined by the human expert and AI-based assessments. Both assessments defined security requirements that could be traced to the identified threat scenarios and addressed common industrial control system protection objectives, including access control, protection of engineering interfaces, and separation between enterprise and automation domains. In both cases, requirements were mapped to reduce the likelihood of unauthorized access or manipulation of safety-critical functions.

Differences are observed in the formulation and abstraction of the requirements. The human expert assessment emphasized operational and organizational measures, such as controlled maintenance access and role-based authorization, which were closely linked to specific threat scenarios and operational workflows. The AI-based assessment emphasized standardized technical controls, including authentication mechanisms, secure update processes, logging, monitoring, and integrity protection, resulting in more uniformly structured requirements.

With respect to the price-value criterion, the human expert requirements tended to reflect pragmatic selection of controls aligned with operational feasibility, whereas the AI-based requirements prioritized completeness and alignment with recognized security control concepts. Both approaches remain consistent with IEC 62443 foundational requirements, but they reflect different emphases on operational applicability versus formal standardization in early-stage risk assessment.

5.5 Zones and Conduits

This subsection compares the zoning and conduit definitions produced by the human expert and AI-based assessments with

Table 4: Comparison of zones and allocated SL-Ts derived by the human expert and AI-based assessments

Human Expert		AI-based	
Zone	SL-T	Zone	SL-T
Enterprise-Mobile	2	Enterprise IT	2
Enterprise Demilitarized Zone (DMZ)	2	Remote Access	3
SCADA	3	Supervisory	3
OT	3	Engineering	3
OT-Mobile	3	Control	4
-	-	Field	2
-	-	Historian	2
-	-	Wireless	3

respect to architectural coherence, quality of justification, and consistency with IEC 62443 zoning principles, including implications for system complexity and life cycle effort.

Both assessments applied a comparable high-level zoning approach by separating enterprise IT, engineering functions, and automation components into distinct security zones and identifying interconnecting communication paths as conduits. In both cases, zones containing safety-critical automation functions were clearly distinguished from higher-level IT domains, consistent with the IEC 62443 concept of security zones and controlled interfaces.

Differences emerge primarily in zoning granularity and the associated justification. The human expert assessment defined a smaller number of zones aligned with functional and operational groupings, with justifications focused on limiting operational access and preventing unintended interference with safety-critical functions. The AI-based assessment defined a more granular zoning structure based on trust boundaries and access paths, with conduits explicitly treated as high-risk interfaces.

While both approaches are consistent with IEC 62443 zoning principles, the differing levels of granularity have practical implications. Each additional zone and conduit introduces further interfaces that must be justified, documented, and assessed individually. Increased zoning granularity therefore expands the scope of detailed risk assessment, security requirement definition, and life cycle management activities, contributing to higher engineering effort and maintenance cost. The comparison highlights differing implicit assumptions regarding the acceptable trade-off between formal separation and the complexity and cost associated with maintaining highly segmented architectures in early-stage industrial risk assessments.

5.6 Security Level Target

This subsection compares SL-Ts assignments in the human expert and AI-based assessments with respect to plausibility relative to identified risks, granularity across zones and conduits, internal consistency, and price-value considerations.

Tables 4 and 5 summarize the zones and conduits defined by the human expert and AI-based assessments together with their allocated security level targets.

Table 5: Comparison of conduits and allocated SL-Ts derived by the human expert and AI-based assessments

Human Expert		AI-based	
Conduit	SL-T	Conduit	SL-T
WLAN	2	IT-OT	3
Enterprise-DMZ	2	Remote Access	3
DMZ-SCADA	3	Control Network	4
SCADA-OT	3	Data	2
Temp-LAN	3	-	-

Both assessments assigned higher SL-Ts to safety-critical automation zones and to conduits bridging automation and higher-level domains, while lower SL-Ts were applied to enterprise IT zones. In both cases, SL-T assignments broadly reflected the relative criticality of system components and interfaces.

Differences are primarily observed in granularity and escalation. The human expert assessment applied relatively uniform SL-Ts across multiple automation-related zones, implicitly limiting the number of components requiring very high security levels. The AI-based assessment assigned more differentiated SL-Ts across zones and conduits, including higher SL-Ts for multiple interfaces. While these assignments remain plausible from a risk perspective, they expand the scope of components subject to high security requirements.

Given that higher SL-Ts (particularly SL-T 4) are associated with substantial increases in implementation effort and life cycle cost, the comparison highlights differing implicit assumptions regarding the balance between risk reduction and economic feasibility. This distinction is especially relevant in early IEC 62443-3-2 assessments, where SL-T selection directly influences downstream architectural and procurement decisions.

5.7 Final System Architecture

This subsection compares the final system architectures produced by the human expert and AI-based assessments as integrative artifacts, focusing on structural coherence, alignment with identified risks, and traceability to earlier assessment steps.

Both architectures reflect the respective threat analyses, zoning concepts, and security level target assignments, demonstrating traceability from earlier assessment steps to architectural outcomes. In both cases, safety-critical automation components are separated from higher-level IT domains, and communication between zones is subject to defined security controls.

The human expert architecture (see Figure 4) consolidates zoning and SL-T decisions into a hierarchical structure with clearly defined trust relationships and access paths. The resulting architecture aligns with the layered separation commonly described by the Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture, despite this model not being explicitly referenced during the assessment. Transitions between major architectural layers are consistently mediated by dedicated security boundaries, with firewalls explicitly placed between enterprise, supervisory, and control-related zones. This makes security enforcement points and trust boundaries visible at the architectural level and supports traceability between zoning decisions and implemented controls.

Figure 4: Final system architecture derived from the human expert assessment, illustrating consolidated zoning, conduits, and security level targets.

The AI-based architecture incorporates a larger number of zones and conduits derived from fine-grained threat differentiation. While this structure maintains formal traceability to individual risks, the placement of certain functional zones introduces architectural ambiguity. In particular, remote access and engineering access zones are positioned between supervisory and control-related zones, resulting in access paths that are not clearly aligned with a hierarchical trust model. In addition, the placement of historian functionality downstream of control zones diverges from common supervisory-data flow patterns and complicates the interpretation of trust and data directionality.

From an industrial deployment perspective, such architectural ambiguity would typically require additional human interpretation and consolidation before implementation. If adopted without such consolidation, it may introduce latent integration, governance, or operability risks, particularly in complex industrial environments, despite formal traceability to identified threats.

Furthermore, while the AI-derived SL-Ts assignments imply the need for strong security controls at zone boundaries, the architecture does not consistently make corresponding enforcement mechanisms—such as dedicated firewalls between major layers—explicit. This leaves it unclear whether security controls are assumed to be implicitly covered by SL-T measures or explicitly realized as architectural elements.

Figure 5 shows the final system architecture derived from the AI-based assessment, illustrating fine-grained zoning, conduits, and differentiated security level targets.

As an integrative outcome, the comparison illustrates that architectural coherence depends not only on the completeness of individual assessment steps, but on how security assumptions are externalized and consolidated in the final system representation. The human expert architecture emphasizes explicit trust boundaries, enforceable separation, and alignment with established OT architectural patterns, whereas the AI-based architecture emphasizes formal risk decomposition with less explicit consolidation of security enforcement at the architectural level.

5.8 Cross-Task Synthesis

Across all assessment tasks, a consistent pattern emerges in the way human expert and AI-based analyses approach IEC 62443-3-2-aligned risk assessment [3]. The AI-based assessment applies a structured and formally consistent analytical approach across tasks, characterized by explicit differentiation of threats, consequences, zones, conduits, and security level targets. Assumptions related to exposure and threat capability are systematically reflected in intermediate results, supporting traceability across the assessment workflow.

The human expert assessment, in contrast, exhibits strong consolidation across tasks, with decisions repeatedly shaped by implicit consideration of system operability and life cycle feasibility. This is reflected in the use of fewer zones and conduits, conservative clustering of security levels, and a final architecture that aligns with established hierarchical OT patterns commonly described by the Purdue Enterprise Reference Architecture. These patterns suggest that practical operation, maintenance, and manageability are continuously considered alongside risk reduction throughout the assessment process.

Across multiple tasks, cost-value considerations emerge implicitly as a differentiating factor. The human expert assessment consistently limits structural and security level granularity, thereby constraining downstream implementation effort and life cycle cost. The AI-based assessment, while plausible from a risk differentiation perspective, does not explicitly reflect economic or organizational constraints, resulting in expanded zoning, elevated security level assignments, and increased assessment and implementation scope.

Finally, these differences propagate into the integrative architectural outcome. The AI-derived architecture reflects formal decomposition of risks and trust boundaries but results in an overall structure with ambiguous trust relationships and access paths that deviate from common OT architectural conventions. The human-derived architecture, by contrast, demonstrates stronger architectural coherence through consolidation of assessment outputs into a manageable and operationally interpretable system structure.

Figure 5: Final system architecture derived from the AI-based assessment, illustrating fine-grained zoning, conduits, and differentiated security level targets.

5.9 Reproducibility and Data Availability

This study does not rely on publicly available datasets. The assessment inputs consisted of a hypothetical system description and associated documentation created for the purpose of this study. Due to their illustrative and context-specific nature, these materials are not published as standalone datasets.

The assessment procedures, task structure, and comparative methodology are fully documented in the manuscript. The AI prompting protocol and assessment outputs were retained by the authors to support traceability of the reported observations, but are not released as datasets as they are specific to the illustrative system context. Reproduction of the results using alternative system descriptions, model versions, or prompting configurations may lead to different outcomes.

6 CONCLUSION

This paper presented an exploratory comparison of human expert and AI-based cybersecurity risk assessments for a safety-critical industrial control system using an IEC 62443-3-2-aligned methodology. Across all assessment tasks, both approaches consistently identified safety-critical components, dominant risk drivers, and the need for strong separation between automation and higher-level IT domains. At the same time, systematic differences emerged in how risks were structured, differentiated, and consolidated across the assessment workflow.

The AI-based assessment emphasized formal structure and differentiation, whereas the human expert assessment focused on consolidation, operational context, and architectural coherence. These differences became most visible in the resulting system architecture.

6.1 Implications for AI-based IEC 62443 Risk Assessment

The findings suggest that AI-based approaches can contribute to early-stage IEC 62443 risk assessments by providing structured and traceable analytical artifacts. However, the results also highlight limitations in capturing implicit operational constraints, cost-value considerations, and architectural conventions commonly applied by experienced practitioners.

Rather than acting as a replacement for human expertise, AI-based analysis appears best suited as a complementary tool. When used in conjunction with human judgment, AI may support completeness and consistency while human analysts retain responsibility for architectural consolidation, operability, and alignment with real-world constraints.

6.2 Future Work

Future work may extend the comparison across multiple systems, assessor groups, and AI models to evaluate the robustness of the observed patterns. Repeated AI assessments under controlled conditions could be used to examine reproducibility and sensitivity to prompting and model configuration.

In addition, future studies might also explore hybrid assessment workflows in which AI-generated outputs are explicitly reviewed, refined, and consolidated by human experts to combine formal analytical structure with operational and architectural expertise.

6.3 Contributions

This work contributes three key insights:

- (1) AI-based IEC 62443 risk assessment artifacts tend to maximize formal risk differentiation across threats, zones, and interfaces, systematically increasing architectural granularity and the number of components subject to elevated SL-Ts.
- (2) Human expert assessments act as a consolidation mechanism that implicitly integrates operability, architectural convention, and life cycle cost considerations.
- (3) Architectural coherence in IEC 62443-based assessments emerges not from risk identification alone, but from the explicit consolidation of security assumptions into enforceable structural boundaries.

7 ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors gratefully acknowledge the contributions of the human experts who participated in the risk assessment tasks forming the basis of this study. We also thank colleagues and collaborators for their technical input and constructive discussions, which helped improve the quality and clarity of this paper.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Xu, S. Wang, N. Li, K. Wang, Y. Zhao, K. Chen, T. Yu, Y. Liu, and H. Wang, "Large language models for cyber security: A systematic literature review," *arXiv*, 2025.
- [2] I. Elsharef, Z. Zeng, and Z. Gu, "Facilitating threat modeling by leveraging large language models," in *Workshop on AI Systems with Confidential Computing (AISCC) 2024*, 2024.
- [3] *IEC 62443-3-2: Security for Industrial Automation and Control Systems – Part 3-2: Security Risk Assessment for System Design*, International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Standard 62 443-3-2, 2020.
- [4] W. Knowles, D. Prince, D. Hutchison, J. F. P. Disso, and K. Jones, "A survey of cyber security management in industrial control systems," *International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection*, vol. 9, pp. 52–80, 2015.
- [5] S. Kriaa, L. Pietre-Cambacedes, M. Bouissou, and Y. Halgand, "A survey of approaches combining safety and security for industrial control systems," *Reliability Engineering & System Safety*, vol. 139, pp. 156–178, 2015.
- [6] *Guide to Operational Technology (OT) Security*, NIST Special Publication 800-82 Revision 3, 2023.
- [7] *IEC/TS 62443-1-1: Security for Industrial Automation and Control Systems – Terminology, Concepts and Models*, International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Technical Specification 62 443-1-1, 2009.
- [8] *IEC 62443-2-1: Security for Industrial Automation and Control Systems – Establishing an IACS Security Program*, International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Standard 62 443-2-1, 2024.
- [9] *IEC 62443-3-3: Security for Industrial Automation and Control Systems – Part 3-3: System Security Requirements and Security Levels*, International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) Standard 62 443-3-3, 2013.
- [10] *ISO 31000: Risk Management – Guidelines*, International Organization for Standardization Standard 31 000, 2018.
- [11] T. Aven, "Risk assessment and risk management: Review of recent advances on their foundation," *European Journal of Operational Research*, vol. 253, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2016.
- [12] D. Amodei, C. Olah, J. Steinhardt, P. Christiano, J. Schulman, and D. Mané, "Concrete problems in AI safety," *arXiv*, 2016.
- [13] D. W. Hubbard, *The Failure of Risk Management: Why It's Broken and How to Fix It*. John Wiley & Sons, 2009.
- [14] MITRE Corporation, "MITRE ATT&CK for industrial control systems," <https://attack.mitre.org/matrices/ics/>, 2025, accessed: 2025-11.